

Narrow Linewidths Ridge Waveguide AlGaAs Diode Lasers with Surface Gratings; Realisation and Device Examples

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Edge emitting diode lasers with defined center wavelengths and narrow linewidths are attractive light sources for a number of applications, such as optical atomic clocks, atom interferometry, gravitational wave detection, space-based metrology, optical quantum sensing and coherent optical communication. The required spectral properties can only be achieved with the integration of Bragg gratings into the laser cavities, either in distributed feedback (DFB) or in distributed Bragg reflector (DBR) configuration. In the recent years, we have developed different grating manufacturing technologies for AlGaAs diode lasers and summarized the different technologies earlier on this conference [1]. Here we want to focus on the processing of surface gratings (SG) and its integration to lateral fundamental mode ridge waveguide (RW) lasers. The SG technology is well suited for the production of monolithically integrated narrow linewidths diode lasers without considerably degrading its efficiency and power.

The SG grating process starts on GaAs wafers with the full vertical layer stack grown by MOVPE. A hard mask made of a baked 700 nm thick photoresist and a 50 nm thick Ti layer is patterned with Ebeam lithography and a three-step reactive ion etching (RIE) process: (i) with SF₆ and (ii) with oxygen plasma. The final etch into p-cladding and confinement layers follows (iii) with a mixture of BCl₃/Cl₂/Ar. The hard mask opening determines the depths of the grating grooves in the semiconductor (Fig. 1). Typical structure sizes of the opened hard mask are between 120 nm and 200 nm for the longitudinal and a few micrometers (depending on the RW widths) for lateral laser dimension. The selected RIE etch parameters form a V-shaped profile of the grating grooves, that narrows towards the center of the vertical waveguide. The resulting high duty cycle at the center of the vertical guided wave is advantages for functional high order gratings (with typical gratings periods greater than 500 nm). Further, the precise etch depth of the grating grooves is prerequisite for gratings with high reflectivity. With the detailed knowledge of the etch process we are able to control a 1.5 µm target depths with a precision below ±50 nm [2]. After etching of the gratings, it follows a standard RW diode laser process. Alignment marks etched with the gratings are applied for the RW definition with i-line lithography and result in an acceptable overlay (Fig. 2). Focused ion beam (FIB) milling of a 2.2 µm wide RW ensures that the target etch depths of the grating grooves are maintained at the lateral center of the RW (Fig. 3).

We summarize two examples where the SG technology has been applied recently: (i) Fig. 4 shows optical spectra of four 2 mm long adjacent red emitting DBR-lasers (pitch 400 µm), each of the 1 mm long DBR with a slightly shifted grating period (Vistec SB251). The question whether it is possible to set a spreading of the wavelengths below 100 pm could be answered positively. (ii) SG gratings have been applied for the fabrication of an 8 mm long 1064 nm DBR-laser. Measurements show a 3dB linewidth as small as 25 kHz which is (to our knowledge and to date) the smallest linewidth for monolithically-integrated diode lasers [3].

- [1] O. Brox, J. Fricke, H. Wenzel, P. Della Casa, A. Maaßdorf, M. Weyers, M. Matalla, and A. Knigge “Grating integration technologies for edge emitting AlGaAs diode lasers”, 45th Intern. Conf. on Micro & Nano Engineering (2019)
- [2] J. Fricke, H. Wenzel, O. Brox, P. Crump, B. Sumpf, K. Paschke, M. Matalla, G. Erbert, A. Knigge, and G. Tränkle “Surface Bragg gratings for high brightness lasers” Proc. SPIE 11301, Novel In-Plane Semiconductor Lasers XIX, Photonics West, San Francisco, USA, Feb 1-6, 113011H (2020)
- [3] S. Wenzel, O. Brox, P. Della Casa, H. Wenzel, A. Knigge, B. Arar, S. Nechayev, S. Kreutzmann, A. Wicht, “Ultra-narrow linewidth GaAs-based DBR Lasers”, Conf. on Lasers and Electro-Optics (2021)

Figure 1. Surface gratings grooves with varying widths from 120 nm to 200 nm

Figure 2. Surface gratings and resist for RW definition

Figure 3. Angled cross section SEM of a 2.2 μm wide RW; FIB milled SG with 1.27 μm deep grooves (target 1.29 μm)

Figure 4. Optical spectra of four 2 mm long DBR-lasers with gratings of 20th order with different grating periods (150 mA)